

A Deep Learning based Intrusion Detection and Prevention System for Mitigating DoS Attacks

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Abstract—Internet of Things (IoT) networks are highly vulnerable to network attacks, the most common examples being DoS and DDoS attacks. Those attacks flood the limited system resources of IoT devices and overwhelm networks with large numbers of attack packets, causing severe performance impacts. In order to mitigate those attacks in IoT networks, this paper develops a lightweight yet effective Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (IDPS). This IDPS sequentially detects and mitigates the attack via a Deep Random Neural Network (DRNN) and the proposed Drop-Idle-Repeat (DIR) process within milliseconds after the attack begins. The developed IDPS is evaluated for DoS, in particular UDP Flood attacks of different lengths on a real-life experimental test-bed built within this paper. Experimental results first revealed that a 60-second long UDP Flood attack is sufficient to paralyse the Server used in the test-bed. On the other hand, the proposed IDPS can successfully mitigate this attack; therefore, the Server utilizing the IDPS can continue its routine operation without being affected by the attack and resume communication with other devices immediately after the attack ends.

Index Terms—Cybersecurity, Deep Random Neural Network, DoS attacks, Internet of Things (IoT), Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (IDPS), System Measurements.

I. INTRODUCTION

The risk of cyber threats, which may do considerable damage to critical networking infrastructure, has increased with the growing dependence on networked technologies and the increasing use of IoT devices with weak security. Denial of Service (DoS) and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks are two of the most common and damaging cyber threats to networked systems [1]. These attacks disable networked systems by flooding them with large streams of requests, causing productivity decline, financial losses, and reputational damage. In 2022, a total increase of 150% in such attacks was observed worldwide [2], with 109% more occurring at the network layer and 72% more occurring at the application layer. The increasingly large number of such attacks mainly target IoT networks, industrial control systems, and well-known public services as well as vital infrastructure.

DoS attacks flood system resources and computational capacity, overwhelming networks with a high volume of packets containing forged source addresses. This results in issues such

as inaccurate or incomplete readings, delayed or lost data, and system overload [3]. Therefore, effective Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS) are required to mitigate these threats.

A. Literature Review

In the existing literature, while most research works evaluate their methodologies using publicly available datasets, early scholarly discourse, as articulated by [4], highlighted the merit of employing test-beds for evaluating ID algorithms. Specialized test-beds tailored for cyber-physical systems, industrial control, and IoT environments have been extensively outlined [5], encompassing dedicated platforms for real-time cyber-physical systems [6]. Notable instances involve the introduction of a semi-physical test-bed for industrial control systems [7], and the evaluation of a cost-effective Smart Grid test-bed for Substation Automation Systems (SCIDS) against TCP flood attacks [8].

Detailed examinations of test-beds for Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems are discussed in [9]–[11]. In the domain of WAN network security, [12] proposed a test-bed utilizing six NetFlow tools for systematic data collection, analysis, and visualization and was tested on HTTP-GET flood attacks. Expanding the purview of IoT systems, [13] explored the nuanced impact of attack datasets and investigated real-time data collection for DNS amplification, while [14] and [15] respectively discussed DoS attacks on software-defined networks and autonomous vehicle testbeds.

Birkinshaw et al. [16] developed an IDPS to mitigate port-scanning and DoS attacks and implemented a test-bed on a Software Defined Network (SDN), while [17] introduced an adaptive IDPS for IoT using an intelligent agent. Kumar et al. [18] created a network-level IDPS for monitoring IoT network activity, dropping malicious packets, blocking their source, and resetting connections upon detection. Islabudeen and Devi [19] proposed a neural network-based IDPS for mobile ad hoc networks against DoS attacks. Abdulqadder et al. [20] employed deep reinforcement learning in their multi-layer IDPS to mitigate flow table overloading attacks in SDNs, evaluated via simulations against IP Spoofing, flow table overloading, and DDoS. Lee et al. [21] compared MLP, CNN, LSTM, and SAE models for SSH brute-force and DDoS

attacks in SDNs. Mihoub et al. [22] aimed to detect and mitigate DoS and DDoS attacks in IoT networks by adjusting traffic rates based on attack type, and they used the BoT-IoT dataset. Finally, the preliminary work [23] demonstrated the effectiveness of DL-based IDPS on an experimental test-bed of two IoT devices, showing that the DL-based IDPS is promising for mitigating DoS attacks.

B. Contributions of this Paper

In this paper, we develop a Deep Learning (DL)-based IDPS to mitigate DoS and DDoS attacks on IoT systems and Local Area Networks (LANs). Accordingly, the main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- A novel lightweight IDPS is developed based on the Deep Random Neural Network (DRNN) algorithm, and the Drop-Idle-Repeat (DIR) process is introduced. This IDPS aims to protect the system against DoS and DDoS attacks that overwhelm its resources while keeping packet loss to a minimum.
- A realistic (small-sized) LAN test-bed is created to evaluate the effects of flood attacks and the performance of IDPS in mitigating them during real attack scenarios. On the contrary, the majority of literature concerning IDS or IDPS assesses their performance in scenarios where attack traffic is obtained from a dataset.
- The characteristics of the effects of UDP Flood attacks of different lengths on system processing are analysed through test-bed measurements. The analysis shows that a sufficiently long UDP Flood attack causes periodic outages (moments when the system is paralysed) if there is no IDPS utilized. The analysis also shows that the proposed IDPS successfully mitigates attacks of different lengths with very low packet loss.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the experimental setup, including the used devices, traffic generation, and analysis of the impacts of UDP Flood attacks of varying lengths. Section III presents the proposed IDPS, covering network traffic metrics, DRNN-based intrusion detection algorithm, and the DIR process as a preventive action. Section IV specifies the learning algorithm and parameter configurations for the IDPS. Section V evaluates the IDPS performance against Flood attacks, while Section VI offers concluding remarks.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In order to analyse the impacts of DoS attacks and evaluate the performance of the IDPS developed in this paper, we build a Local Area Network (LAN) environment for experimental testing. As shown in Figure 1, this environment presently consists of four IoT devices and a Server; however, it can easily be expanded to include an arbitrary number of connected devices with multiple sources of traffic and attacks. Three of the IoT devices (RPi1, RPi2, and RPi3) generate and transmit normal – benign – IP packet traffic, while the last device (RPi4) generates a combination of benign and malicious traffic.

Fig. 1. A LAN test-bed employing Ethernet for communication utilizes four Raspberry Pi machines as sources for both normal and attack traffic. An Intel 8-Core Processor serves as the central server, responsible for processing incoming packet traffic and detecting potential attacks.

A. Hardware Configurations

The ensemble of IoT devices comprises four Raspberry Pi 4 Model B Rev 1.2 units that serve as transmitters, boasting a 1.5 GHz ARM Cortex-A72 quad-core processor, 2GB LPDDR4 - 3200 SDRAM, and run Raspbian GNU/Linux 11 (bullseye).

On the receiving end, an Intel Core i7 - 8705G-powered robust server with 16GB of RAM, eight 3.10 GHz cores, and a 500GB hard drive, operating on Linux 5.15.0-60-generic 66-Ubuntu SMP, assumes the pivotal role of detecting and storing incoming packets. The inter-device communication is facilitated over Ethernet connections, with all devices interconnected through a central hub, as shown in Figure 1.

Both the Raspberry Pi devices and the server were carefully selected to ensure efficient transmission and reception of data packets over Ethernet. These devices communicate using the UDP protocol due to its simplicity and low overhead. In contrast to TCP, UDP operates without establishing a connection before transmitting data and without providing any ACK or error recovery mechanisms and is a fast and efficient protocol for real-time applications [24], which also makes it more susceptible to DoS and DDoS attacks.

B. Traffic Generation

In standard operation, in the absence of any attacks, each of the RPi1, RPi2, RPi3, and RPi4 devices consistently produces regular IP packet traffic, conveying the CPU temperature of the device. This information is transmitted to the server every second via the UDP protocol. On the other hand, the attack traffic generator exploits the public repository MHDDoS [25], which contains 56 methods for generating different types of DoS attacks that can be directed toward the transport and application layers of the OSI model.

During our experiments, RPi1, RPi2, and RPi3 generate only normal traffic, while the compromised device RPi4 generates both normal and attack traffic. This device initiates a UDP Flood attack of a specific length after transmitting 400 normal packets.

C. Analysing the Impacts of IoT Flood Attacks

To observe the impacts of UDP Flood attacks of different lengths on the system, we now analyse the Server behaviour during two separate experiments with UDP attacks, respectively, lasting 10 and 60 seconds. Note that the Server utilizes only an ID algorithm during these experiments. As one shall see through the results in this subsection, devastating impacts of a DoS attack can easily be observed during a UDP Flood attack lasting 60 seconds. Therefore, we do not extend our analysis beyond this duration.

1) Experiment I – UDP Flood Attack Lasting 10 Seconds:

Figure 2 displays the queue length and packet delay measured at the Server – utilizing only an intrusion detection algorithm – for 2000 seconds during which a 10-second UDP Flood attack from RPi4 is observed. We measured that the compromised RPi4 transmits 157,135 attack packets during this 10-second UDP Flood attack.

The measurements in Figure 2 (top) show that the number of packets waiting to be analysed by the Server increases sharply when the attack is initiated and gradually decreases after the attack ends. At the end of the attack, queue length peaks at 155,788. We also observe that the packet delay shows similar behaviour (reaching 15 minutes) in Figure 2 (bottom) due to a large queue length. Although the attack only lasts 10 seconds, its impact on the Server lasts approximately 27 minutes due to the volume of traffic received in that 10-second interval.

Fig. 2. The number of packets waiting to be analysed by the Server, i.e., queue length (top) and the delay experienced by each packet (bottom), are measured for a UDP Flood attack originating from RPi4 lasting 10 seconds. The red dashed lines in these figures show when the attack started and ended.

2) Experiment II – UDP Flood Attack Lasting 60 Seconds:

Figure 3 displays the effect of a UDP Flood attack that lasts 60 seconds on the packet processing rate, the queue length at the Server, and packet delay for over 20000 seconds. The measurements in Figure 3 (top) show that the processing rate

at the Server drops intermittently to zero. Moments when the processing rate drops to zero are a direct indication that **the Server is paralysed** by the ongoing impact of the attack. We observed that when the Server was paralysed, all computing resources were used to manage incoming packet traffic, so it could not do any operation, including packet processing.

Fig. 3. The effect of the attack on packet processing rate (top), the corresponding queue length in the Server (middle), and the delay experienced by each packet (bottom) are measured for a UDP Flood attack originating from RPi4 lasting 60 seconds. The red dashed lines in these figures show when the attack started and ended.

Furthermore, as one may see from Figure 3 (bottom), packet delay rapidly increases, becoming unacceptably long. The delay is approximately 5.85 hours for even the packets that are transmitted within the first 26 seconds after the attack is initiated. Our measurements in Figure 3 (bottom) also show that the Server was not able to receive and process any packet shortly after the attack started.

After observing the Server's behaviour under a DoS – in particular UDP Flood – attack, we concluded that these severe attack symptoms could occur even if the malicious packet transmission from the attacker lasts only for 60 seconds, during which the Server receives more than 404,500 malicious packets. As our measurements showed, the effects of an attack on the Server can last much longer than the activity of the attacker in the absence of any mitigation action as per the intrusion detection. Considering that the most recent DoS

Fig. 4. Schematic system organization of the Server that utilizes the proposed DL-based IDPS

attacks last much longer than 60 seconds, it is crucial to utilize an IDPS on the Server to prevent excessively long service interruptions.

III. INTRUSION DETECTION AND PREVENTION SYSTEM (IDPS)

We now introduce our Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (IDPS), which is designed to mitigate the effects of a DoS attack from its early stages. The proposed IDPS consists of two algorithms that cooperate to prevent intrusions based on continuous detection of malicious traffic. IDPS is hosted on the Server to analyse all incoming packet traffic.

The overall architecture of the Server utilizing the proposed IDPS is displayed in Figure 4. As shown in this figure, the Server acquires packets from the connected devices on port 5555. Subsequently, these packets are handed over to the “Buffer Manager” through the network protocol, where they are queued for analysis at the IDPS. Within the IDPS, each packet i is first classified as “benign” or “malicious” by our Intrusion Detection (ID) algorithm based on high-level traffic metrics. According to the ID decisions for M consecutive packets, intrusion prevention is performed to protect the Server from current and upcoming malicious traffic.

A. Network Traffic Metrics

We use traffic metrics, as defined and extended in [26] to capture the signatures of DDoS attacks, especially Mirai Botnet attacks on IoT networks, which have also been extended to identify various DoS and DDoS attacks. These metrics measure the density of packet traffic using only header information (packet length and transmission time); therefore, it protects the confidentiality of packet contents and provides ID with unbiased statistics that can be easily calculated in real-time.

Let t_i be the instant when packet i is transmitted and b_i be its length in bytes. The first metric is the total size of the last I packets observed by our ID algorithm up to and including the latest packet i , and the second metric is the average inter-transmission time of those packets:

$$x_i^1 = \sum_{j=0}^{I-1} b_{(i-j)}, \quad \text{and} \quad x_i^2 = \frac{1}{I} \sum_{j=0}^{I-1} [t_{(i-j)} - t_{(i-j-1)}]. \quad (1)$$

The third metric is the total number of packets transmitted in the last T seconds up to the transmission of packet i :

$$x_i^3 = |\{j : (t_i - T) \leq t_j < t_i\}|. \quad (2)$$

Each metric is also normalized via min-max scaling using the training dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ as

$$x_i^m \leftarrow \min \left[\frac{x_i^m - \min_{j \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}} x_j^m}{\max_{j \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}} x_j^m - \min_{j \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}} x_j^m}, 1 \right], \quad \forall m. \quad (3)$$

B. Intrusion Detection

We now detail the ID algorithm used in this paper. This algorithm is an enhanced version of the one proposed in [26], and is based on the DRNN [27] with auto-associative learning, called AADRNN. As it is an anomaly-based intrusion detector, it **learns only from the normal traffic**.

For each packet i , the ID algorithm computes decision $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ based on the input vector of the three metrics ($x^i = [x_i^1, x_i^2, x_i^3]$) calculated from network traffic. To this end, it is comprised of the AADRNN followed by a decision making module. As the ID algorithm learns only normal traffic, the AADRNN, in real-time, estimates the metrics that are expected to be measured from traffic in the absence of an intrusion, namely $\hat{x}_i = [\hat{x}_i^1, \hat{x}_i^2, \hat{x}_i^3]$. That is, when a measurement x^i is entered into the AADRNN, it outputs the response \hat{x}_i . Then, the decision making module computes the decision variable y_i (attack or non-attack) using the difference between the input x^i and the output \hat{x}_i .

1) *Estimating Normal Traffic Metrics*: The AADRNN is built using the DRNN neuronal network model [27], a generalization of the RNN [28], which incorporates soma-to-soma triggering between neurons, as well as the commonly used excitatory and inhibitory spikes. It uses auto-associative learning and provides accurate detection in significant test cases [26]. The DRNN is organized in $l \in \{1, \dots, L\}$ feed-forward layers, each comprised of N_l clusters, each cluster having n_l identical neurons. Weight matrices W_l connect the clusters of layer l to those of layer $l+1$, and the weights are learned to create an auto-associative memory. For the input vector x_i , the forward pass of the AADRNN is:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x}_i^l &= \zeta([\hat{x}_i^{l-1}, 1] W_{l-1}), \quad 1 \leq l \leq L, \\ \hat{x}_i &= [\hat{x}_i^{L-1}, 1] W_{L-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \hat{x}_i^l is the output of layer l for packet i , $\hat{x}_i^0 = x_i$, and $[\hat{x}_i^l, 1]$ indicates that 1 is concatenated to the output of each layer l as a multiplier of the bias, and $\zeta(\lambda)$ is the DRNN specific neuron activation function [27].

2) *Decision Making*: From the output \hat{x}_i of the AADRNN with input x_i , the binary decision variable y_i is obtained using the threshold $1 > \gamma > 0$:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{1}{3} \sum_{m=1}^3 |x_i^m - \hat{x}_i^m| \geq \gamma \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

C. Intrusion Prevention

Based on the binary intrusion decision y_i , which is provided by the ID algorithm for packet i , our IDPS takes preventive action to mitigate the devastating impacts of an attack, which were observed in Section II-C. In order to meet real-time requirements and be able to operate in IoT networks, the preventive action should be lightweight (simple) yet effective. Therefore, in this paper, we develop a Drop-Idle-Repeat (DIR) process.

The DIR process aims to prevent the host device – which is the Server in this paper – from the impacts of an attack in its early stages with a low packet loss. To this end, if an intrusion is detected by the ID algorithm, all the packets in the input buffer of the IDPS are simply dropped and the system is backed off into the idle state for a certain period of time. During an idle state, the Server shuts down its communication with other devices but runs its own processing tasks. In this way, critical operations performed by the Server and the data stored in it are secured.

Algorithm 1 The IDPS

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1:  $p \leftarrow 0$ 
2: while  $|B_{in}| > 0$  do
3:    $p \leftarrow p + 1$ 
4:    $x_p \leftarrow \mathbf{CalcMetrics}(B_{in}, p)$ 
5:    $y_p \leftarrow \mathbf{ID}(x_p)$ 
6:   if  $(p \geq M)$  and  $(\sum_{j=(p-M+1)}^p y_j \geq \frac{M}{2})$  then
7:      $B_{in} \leftarrow ()$ 
8:     back-off $(\tau)$ 
9:      $p \leftarrow 0$ 
10:  end if
11: end while

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The pseudo-code of the IDPS is shown in Algorithm 1, where it is assumed that the packets are received and the buffer – denoted by B_{in} – is updated by the Buffer Manager in parallel to the operations of the IDPS. As shown in this algorithm (between Lines 2-11), IDPS analyses each packet that is added to the input buffer B_{in} . For each packet indexed by p in B_{in} , first, the intrusion decision is obtained.

IV. LEARNING ALGORITHM & PARAMETER SETTINGS

We now present the learning algorithm and parameter selection to determine the critical parameters of our IDPS.

A. Auto-Associative Learning Algorithm and Parameters for Intrusion Detection

In our experiments, we use a three-layer AADRNN (i.e. $L = 3$), where each layer contains 3 clusters. For this AADRNN, we set the hyper-parameters as follows: $r = 0.001$, $\lambda^+ = \lambda^- = 0.1$, and $p = 0.05$.

The connection weights of the AADRNN model are learned using only normal (benign) traffic at its first deployment. To this end, at the beginning of each experiment, the first 500

traffic packets received by the Server are ensured to be normal traffic, so the time until these packets are received by the Server can be seen as the “cold start” of the network.

Using the 500 normal traffic packets received during the cold-start period, the connection weight matrix W_l between layers l and $l + 1$ is calculated, solving the following problem by the Fast Iterative Shrinkage-Thresholding Algorithm (FISTA) [29]:

$$W_l = \underset{\{W: W \geq 0\}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left(\left\| \operatorname{adj}(\zeta(\hat{X}_{l-1}^{\text{train}} W_R)), \mathbf{1}_{(|\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}| \times 1)} \right\| W - \hat{X}_{l-1}^{\text{train}} \right\|_{L_2}^2 + \|W\|_{L_1} \right) \quad (6)$$

where \hat{X}_l^{train} is the matrix of outputs of layer l resulting from the training dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ that contains the first 500 normal packets:

$$\hat{X}_l^{\text{train}} = \{\hat{x}_i^l\}_{i \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}}, \quad (7)$$

and $\mathbf{1}_{(|\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}| \times 1)}$ is a column vector of ones with length $|\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}|$.

B. Parameters of Intrusion Prevention

As one can see in Algorithm 1, there are two main parameters M and τ of our IDPS for intrusion prevention. The first parameter M is critical to make accurate attack decision and trigger intrusion prevention at the right time instance.

When we analyse the delay in attack decision of our IDPS shown in Figure 5 for varying values of M , we observe that the number of false positive attack decisions is the minimum for $M = 40$. While M values smaller than 40 cause false decisions due to individual packets incorrectly classified as an attack by the ID algorithm, larger M values are observed to cause some false decisions made immediately after the attack is over. Therefore, according to our analysis of the results given in Figure 5, the value M is chosen as 40.

Fig. 5. Total number of packets classified as an attack with false decision for different values of M during a UDP Flood attack that lasts 10 seconds

Subsequently, we let T_d be the total time needed to make a decision over M packets. It is known that the average inter-transmission time for any normal packet (denoted by T_n) is much greater than the execution time of our ID algorithm (denoted by T_e). On the other hand, when an attack occurs, the average packet inter-transmission time of malicious traffic (denoted by T_m) will be less than T_e .

One can recall that our IDPS triggers the mitigation action when at least half of the last M packets are malicious.

Accordingly, we calculate T_d for the case, where the decision is made over $M/2$ normal and $M/2$ malicious packets:

$$T_d = \frac{M}{2} \left[T_n + \max(T_m, T_e) \right]. \quad (8)$$

For the normal traffic in our experimental set-up, the value of T_n is already known and equals $0.25 s$. For the attack traffic, the value of T_m varies depending on the type and design of the attack, and it cannot be known in advance. However, during the UDP Flood attacks given in Section II-C, we measured that $T_m = 66 \mu s$ during the peak of the attack. In addition, Google recently measured a peak of 398 million requests per second, corresponding to T_m of approx. $2.9 ns$ during the largest DDoS attack in history [30]. Meanwhile, the time elapsed for intrusion detection on the Server is measured as $T_e = 3.2 ms$. Considering all these measurements, we can say that $T_e \geq T_m$ for the majority of attack cases leading

$$T_d = \frac{M}{2} (T_n + T_e) \quad (9)$$

for our experiments.

Since DoS or DDoS attacks contain a significantly larger number of packets than normal traffic in any given time window, we intuitively say that the back-off period should be greater than the time spent for making an attack decision. That is, the second parameter τ should satisfy $\tau > T_d$. Otherwise, if the attack continues during the decision process between two successive back-off periods, a large amount of malicious traffic may flood the input queue and cause system slowdown (or even shutdown). Accordingly, if $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$ is a constant number, we say that

$$\tau = \frac{1}{\beta} T_d, \quad (10)$$

where we empirically set $\beta = 0.2$ in our experiments. As $M = 40$, $T_n = 0.25 s$, and $T_e = 3.2 ms$, the resulting $\tau = 25.32 s$.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF THE IDPS

We evaluate the behaviour of the Server utilizing the proposed IDPS during an ongoing DoS attack. To this end, we run the same two experiments, namely Experiment I and Experiment II, given in Section II-C. Note that the experiments on the test-bed with the Server utilizing IDPS were run for about 1.5 hours. However, since the system was in a normal state after this period and no anomalies (such as false attack decisions) were observed, we present only the first 600 seconds of both experiments in this section.

A. Experiment I - UDP Flood Attack Lasting 10 Seconds

First, we present the measurements on our test-bed for Experiment I when the Server utilizes the proposed IDPS. As displayed in Figure 6, the effect of our IDPS during the 10-second UDP Flood attack is measured with respect to queue length, packet delay, and cumulative packet loss.

Figure 6 (top) shows the queue length of the IDPS's input buffer when the attack mitigation is performed. It is seen that the 10-second long attack is mitigated successfully. The queue length reaches 663 packets until our IDPS makes an attack

Fig. 6. Queue length (top), packet delay (middle), and packet loss (bottom), measurements on the Server utilizing the proposed IDPS during the 10-second UDP Flood attack

decision over $M = 40$ packets and empties the buffer. We also see in Figure 6 (middle) that the packet delay is under $1 s$ for all packets except those received at the beginning of the attack.

We can see both in Figure 6 (top) and (middle) that the Server stays at the idle state for a while after the attack ends as $\tau = 25.32 s$ is longer than the attack duration of $10 s$. As shown in Figure 6 (bottom), the slightly long idle duration causes a packet loss of 95 in total. One may say that such packet loss is acceptable compared to the severe impact of the attack lasting 27 minutes and causing up to 15 minutes of packet delay (as shown in Figure 2).

B. Experiment II - UDP Flood Attack Lasting 60 Seconds

We then present the measurements on our test-bed with the Server utilizing the IDPS for Experiment II. Figure 7 displays the behaviour of the Server with IDPS during the 60-second UDP Flood attack. The experimental results in Figure 7 (top) reveal that the proposed IDPS successfully mitigates the attack with a considerably low queue length. Although the UDP Flood attack lasts 60 seconds and transmits more than 400,000 packets in total, the proposed IDPS mitigates the attack immediately after 912 packets are received into the input

queue. In this way, the IDPS prevents the Server from getting paralysed.

Fig. 7. Queue length (top), packet delay (middle), and packet loss (bottom), measurements on the Server utilizing the proposed IDPS during the 60-second UDP Flood attack; the decision to perform mitigation via the DIR process results in subsequent very short packet queue length, avoiding Server paralysis

Meanwhile, as one can see in Figure 7 (top), the IDPS takes two sequential successful decisions for mitigation during the attack as its duration of 60 seconds is longer than $\tau = 25.32 s$. The results in this figure show that the successive decisions are taken quickly enough that the input queue length reaches only up to 39 packets between two decisions. In addition, as shown in Figure 7 (middle), these decisions keep packet delay under 1 second for almost all packets except those received during the attack.

Furthermore, the results in Figure 7 reveal that the IDPS made a false positive decision just after the attack ended. This false decision results in an extra $\tau = 25.32 s$ spent in an idle state, causing additional packet loss. On the other hand, as presented in Figure 7 (bottom), cumulative packet loss during a total of three idle states reaches only up to 297 packets.

VI. CONCLUSION

DoS and DDoS attacks are significant threats to IoT networks, leading to service interruptions, and delayed, lost, or inaccurate data. In this paper, we analyzed the impact of a UDP Flood attack on a real-life test-bed. Our measurements

show that a 60-second attack can paralyze a server equipped with an Intel Core i7 – 8705G processor, a 16GB of RAM, and eight cores each running at 3.10 GHz.

To effectively mitigate these attacks, we developed a lightweight DL-based IDPS, featuring a DRNN for unsupervised detection and a DIR process for mitigation. Upon detecting an intrusion among the most recent $M = 40$, DIR drops all input buffer packets and idles the system for $\tau = 25.32 s$, allowing the server to continue its operations securely.

Our experimental measurements revealed that the IDPS successfully mitigates UDP Flood attacks, maintaining server functionality and resuming communication post-attack with minimal packet loss (the expected cost of the IDPS) of up to 300 packets during the 60-second attack and with delays under 1 second.

Future work will focus on securing all nodes in distributed systems, such as WSNs, Supply chains, or Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANET).

REFERENCES

- [1] ExtraHop, Denial of Service Attack: Definition, Examples, and Prevention, accessed: 2023-03-09 (January 2022). URL <https://www.extrahop.com/resources/attacks/dos/>
- [2] S. Staff, Organizations fought an average of 29.3 attacks daily in late 2022 (Feb 2023). URL <https://www.securitymagazine.com/articles/98958-organizations-fought-an-average-of-293-attacks-daily-in-late-2022>
- [3] J. Mirkovic, et al., Accurately measuring denial of service in simulation and testbed experiments, *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing* 6 (2) (2008) 81–95.
- [4] J. Mirkovic, S. Fahmy, P. Reiher, R. K. Thomas, How to test dos defenses, in: 2009 Cybersecurity App. & Technology Conf., IEEE, 2009, pp. 103–117.
- [5] O. A. Waraga, M. Bettayeb, Q. Nasir, M. A. Talib, Design and implementation of automated iot security testbed, *Computers & Security* 88 (2020) 101648.
- [6] C. B. Vellaithurai, S. S. Biswas, A. K. Srivastava, Development and application of a real-time test bed for cyber-physical system, *IEEE Systems Journal* 11 (4) (2015) 2192–2203.
- [7] M. Kaouk, F.-X. Morgand, J.-M. Flaus, A testbed for cybersecurity assessment of industrial and iot-based control systems, in: *Lambda Mu 2018-21è Congrès de Maîtrise des Risques et Sécurité de Fonctionnement*, 2018.
- [8] M. Annor-Asante, B. Pranggono, Development of smart grid testbed with low-cost hardware and software for cybersecurity research and education, *Wireless Personal Communications* 101 (2018) 1357–1377.
- [9] A. Ghaleb, S. Zhioua, A. Almulhem, Scada-sst: a scada security testbed, in: 2016 World Congress on Industrial Control Systems Security (WCICSS), IEEE, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [10] A. Tesfahun, D. L. Bhaskari, A scada testbed for investigating cyber security vulnerabilities in critical infrastructures, *Automatic Control and Computer Sciences* 50 (2016) 54–62.
- [11] B. Reutimann, I. Ray, Simulating measurement attacks in a scada system testbed, in: *Critical Infrastructure Protection XV: 15th IFIP WG 11.10 International Conference, ICCIP 2021, Virtual Event, March 15–16, 2021, Revised Selected Papers* 15, Springer, 2022, pp. 135–153.
- [12] S.-U. Park, S.-M. Hwang, Test bed construction for apt attack detection, *International Journal of Control and Automation* 11 (4) (2018) 175–186.
- [13] R. Arthi, S. Krishnaveni, Design and development of iot testbed with ddos attack for cyber security research, in: 2021 3rd International Conference on Signal Processing and Communication (ICPSC), IEEE, 2021, pp. 586–590.
- [14] A. P. Wright, N. Ghani, A testbed for the evaluation of denial of service attacks in software-defined networks, in: 2019 SoutheastCon, IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–6.

- [15] P. V. Sontakke, N. B. Chopade, Impact and analysis of denial-of-service attack on an autonomous vehicle test bed setup, in: Proceedings of Third International Conference on Intelligent Computing, Information and Control Systems: ICICCS 2021, Springer, 2022, pp. 221–236.
- [16] C. Birkinshaw, E. Rouka, V. G. Vassilakis, Implementing an intrusion detection and prevention system using software-defined networking: Defending against port-scanning and denial-of-service attacks, *Journal of Network and Computer Applications* 136 (2019) 71–85.
- [17] S. T. Bakhsh, S. Alghamdi, R. A. Alsemmeari, S. R. Hassan, An adaptive intrusion detection and prevention system for internet of things, *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks* 15 (11) (2019) 1550147719888109.
- [18] A. Kumar, K. Abhishek, M. R. Ghalib, A. Shankar, X. Cheng, Intrusion detection and prevention system for an iot environment, *Digital Communications and Networks* 8 (4) (2022) 540–551.
- [19] M. Islabudeen, M. Kavitha Devi, A smart approach for intrusion detection and prevention system in mobile ad hoc networks against security attacks, *Wireless Personal Communications* 112 (2020) 193–224.
- [20] I. H. Abdulqadder, S. Zhou, D. Zou, I. T. Aziz, S. M. A. Akber, Multi-layered intrusion detection and prevention in the sdn/nfv enabled cloud of 5g networks using ai-based defense mechanisms, *Computer Networks* 179 (2020) 107364.
- [21] T.-H. Lee, L.-H. Chang, C.-W. Syu, Deep learning enabled intrusion detection and prevention system over sdn networks, in: 2020 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops), 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [22] A. Mihoub, O. B. Fredj, O. Cheikhrouhou, A. Derhab, M. Krichen, Denial of service attack detection and mitigation for internet of things using looking-back-enabled machine learning techniques, *Computers & Electrical Engineering* 98 (2022) 107716.
- [23] M. Nasereddin, M. Nakıp, E. Gelenbe, Measurement based evaluation and mitigation of flood attacks on a lan test-bed, in: 2023 IEEE 48th Conference on Local Computer Networks (LCN), IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–4.
- [24] S. Kumar, S. Rai, Survey on transport layer protocols: Tcp & udp, *International Journal of Computer App.* 46 (7) (2012) 20–25.
- [25] MHDDoS - DDoS Attack Script With 56 Methods, Online, accessed: 2023-02-22 (May 2022).
URL <https://github.com/MatrixTM/MHDDoS>
- [26] E. Gelenbe, M. Nakıp, Traffic based sequential learning during botnet attacks to identify compromised iot devices, *IEEE Access* 10 (2022) 126536–126549.
- [27] E. Gelenbe, Y. Yin, Deep learning with random neural networks, in: 2016 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN), IEEE, 2016, pp. 1633–1638.
- [28] E. Gelenbe, Random neural networks with negative and positive signals and product form solution, *Neural computation* 1 (4) (1989) 502–510.
- [29] A. Beck, M. Teboulle, A fast iterative shrinkage-thresholding algorithm for linear inverse problems, *SIAM journal on imaging sciences* 2 (1) (2009) 183–202.
- [30] E. Kiner, T. April, Google mitigated the largest DDoS attack to date, peaking above 398 million rps, accessed: 2023-11-20 (October 2023).
URL <https://cloud.google.com/blog/products/identity-security/google-cloud-mitigated-largest-ddos-attack-peaking-above-398-million-rps>